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ABSTRACT

We present a systematic approach for synthesizing 3D-printable all-dielectric devices. Inverse design approaches yield, in many cases, configurations with a continuous range of dielectric constant values. However, 3D printer resins usually provide a very limited set of such values; commonly, a single resin and air are the only available materials. We propose a methodology for transforming a device with a continuous range of material properties to a manufacturable one, while preserving the device's performance as close as possible to the continuous case. We develop an algorithm that takes the continuous range of dielectric constant profile as input and generates a binary and connected device that can be 3D-printed using a single resin. Our methodology advances state-of-the-art algorithms by using manufacturable configurations of prescribed local air/resin composition to realize each designed dielectric material instead of being limited to a predetermined shape. The additional degrees of freedom provided by our approach may be particularly useful in devices of conformal complex-shaped dielectric constant profiles. We demonstrate the proposed methodology by designing a 3D-printable wide-angle refraction metagrating with performance very close to the inversely designed device of a continuous dielectric constant profile. The approach can be adapted to accommodate three-dimensional devices and other applications.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Over recent years, advances in additive manufacturing have enabled the realization of a variety of all-dielectric, 3D-printed, easily deployable devices with rapid prototyping, that can be used for beam steering, focusing, and antenna applications, ranging from acoustic,^{1,2} microwave, or millimeter-wave applications,^{3,4} to sub-THz frequencies.⁵ Although filament-based 3D-printing techniques are common,^{6,7} stereolithography (SLA) 3D-printing has also been recently used,^{1,8} enabling even higher-precision fabrication. Various all-dielectric devices have been fabricated by SLA 3D-printing, such as multibeam lens antenna for CubeSat applications,⁹ a Luneburg lens for 5G antennas,¹⁰ fresnel-lens antennas,¹¹ a flat Luneburg lens antenna using ceramic SLA 3D-printing,¹² THz metalens.¹³

Inverse design has been employed to enhance the efficiency and functionalities of metamaterial devices.^{14,15} Inverse design methodologies include topology optimization techniques,¹⁶ such as objective-first optimization,^{17,18} and adjoint optimization approaches.¹⁹

Metadevices of non-intuitive patterns have been realized by inverse freeform design to achieve large-angle, multi-functional performance.¹⁹ Such devices support a large number of spatially overlapping modes, which, in turn, provide the necessary degrees of freedom to produce high-efficiency devices. Apart from nanophotonic devices, certain millimeter-wave devices have also been realized, such as lenses and beam steering metagratings for relatively small deflection angles, using filament-based 3D-printing fabrication.^{20,21} As many available inverse-design-optimization algorithms produce devices with a continuous set of material parameters, there is a need to transform the optimized configurations into manufacturable ones without compromising their performance. A binarization cost may be added to an objective-first optimization to favor binary structures.²² A multi-step optimization may also be followed, with the first step allowing for continuous values of the dielectric constant, followed by a discretization step and then a discrete optimization step, where the level set representation of the device is optimized with fabrication constraints in the form of a penalty function.²³

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Other fabrication-oriented constraints that may be added to topology-optimization formulations include the introduction of artificial attenuation of the electromagnetic field for any intermediate dielectric constant level, to promote binary structures, and filtering constraints, to promote larger features.²⁴

A common approach for transforming a device with a continuous dielectric constant or refractive index profile into a 3D printable one is to assign a suitable subwavelength structure, which achieves the desired effective property, to each non-feasible material.^{1,4,25} Each subwavelength structure is composed of the available materials, which in many cases are air and the 3D printer's resin. By considering an air/resin configuration and varying one or more geometric parameters, the desired effective permittivity range is obtained. An S-parameter retrieval method may be used to calculate the effective dielectric constant of each unit cell.⁴ An algorithm that implements this design practice is a pick-and-place algorithm,²⁶ where an air-resin unit cell of the desired effective property is picked out of a predetermined library and placed into the correct position. Inversely designed devices of complex, detailed, and non-intuitive shapes are more challenging to transform into 3D-printable ones by such an approach without compromising the device's performance.

In this work, we introduce a simple and systematic approach for synthesizing 3D-printable all-dielectric devices with a performance very close to that of the continuous case. We render a device with a continuous set of dielectric constant values discrete by keeping as many intermediate dielectric constant levels as needed to attain an identical performance to the continuous case. We implement all designed dielectric materials by configurations of a prescribed air/resin percentage, instead of being limited to a single configuration of predetermined shape. By extending the existing design approach, we enable greater design flexibility, which may be particularly useful in devices with conformal and complex-shaped dielectric materials, as are the outcomes of inverse design optimization techniques. The proposed methodology also considers fabrication aspects, such as the available materials, minimum feature size, and connectivity, so that the realized devices are 3D-printable as a unified component. Our methodology can be applied to both two- and three-dimensional devices and can be used as a post-processing step for inversely designed structures or simply to implement an analytical dielectric constant distribution. As a proof of concept, we demonstrate the proposed design approach on a 2D wide-angle refraction metagrating with a performance very close to the outcome of the inverse design.

II. DETERMINING THE AIR/RESIN PERCENTAGE FOR EACH MATERIAL LEVEL

In many practical scenarios, a limited number of 3D printing materials are available; most commonly, they are air and resin. Therefore, most dielectric constant levels must be implemented by using suitable air/resin structures. We demonstrate how to determine the air/resin percentage that implements the desired effective dielectric constant values. We consider a variety of air/resin configurations of the same resin percentage and examine their effective properties using a periodic eigenmode solver. A dense grid of square cells is assumed of subwavelength size, $\lambda/42 \times \lambda/42$. Air

has a relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 1$; the SLA 3D printer's resin has $\epsilon_r = 2.7$. The selected resin is Formlabs Clear V4, which has been characterized in Ref. 27, with $\epsilon_r = 2.7$ obtained at 12 GHz and $\epsilon_r = 2.65$ at 20 GHz, and $\tan\delta = 0.03$. As we operate around 10 GHz, we use an approximate value of $\epsilon_r = 2.7$. We neglect losses throughout the design process; they can be added to the 3D-printable configuration.

We use a three-dimensional periodic eigenmode solver²⁸ to calculate the dispersion characteristics of each air/resin configuration. The $\omega - k$ periodic eigenmode formulation considers the operating frequency to be known, and we seek the complex propagation constant $k = \beta - j\alpha$, with β being the propagation constant and α the attenuation constant. The formulation is expressed in terms of the electric field envelope \tilde{E} . According to the Bloch-Floquet theorem, the electric field E can be decomposed into the electric field envelope and a phase term, $E = \tilde{E}e^{-jk\cdot r}$. The periodic boundary conditions are substituted by simpler continuity ones. Continuity boundary conditions are applied on all external surfaces.

We consider configurations where air and resin are well separated [Figs. 1(b) and 1(c)] and an S-shaped configuration in Fig. 1(d). The resin to total percentage is 5/9, i.e., about 55.6% in all cases. All dispersion diagrams in terms of the propagation constant are shown in Fig. 1(a) for a mode with the propagation vector

FIG. 1. (a) Dispersion diagrams of configurations A,B,C with 55.6% resin. The propagation constant is matched to that of a suitable homogeneous medium, to determine the effective dielectric constant of each configuration. The propagation constant of an effective medium with average effective dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 1.725$ is also included. (b)–(d) The considered air/resin configurations of 55.6% resin composition, (b) and (c) non-uniformly arranged and (d) S-shaped configurations.

along the y axis and the electric field along the x axis. As dielectric losses are not taken into account, we do not examine the attenuation constant. We also consider the propagation constant of a homogeneous medium with $\beta = k_0 \sqrt{\epsilon_r}$ and determine the ϵ_r value that matches the dispersion diagram of the homogeneous medium to that of each air/resin configuration. We observe that the resin percentage does not exclusively define the effective dielectric constant; the S-shaped arrangement has an effective dielectric constant of $\epsilon_r = 1.7$, whereas the configurations A and B have somewhat higher or lower values, $\epsilon_r = 1.61$ for A and $\epsilon_r = 1.87$ for B. The results of Fig. 1(a) suggest that configurations with a closer-to-uniform distribution of air and resin, such as Fig. 1(d), have an effective dielectric constant very close to the average dielectric constant of all configurations, $\text{Avg}\{\epsilon_r\} = 1.725$ for a resin percentage of 55.6%. The unit cell of Fig. 1(d) forms three material volumes, whereas the unit cells of Figs. 1(b) and 1(c) consist of two volumes. Unit cells with more material volumes and finer internal structures support any resonances at higher frequencies than unit cells with fewer and well-separated materials. Hence, unit cells with finer internal structures are more suitable to approximate the assigned dielectric constant. In our methodology, we aim at unit cells like Fig. 1(d) and avoid unit cells like Figs. 1(b) and 1(c). By the periodic eigenmode solver and the corresponding dispersion diagrams, we assign a resin percentage to each intermediate dielectric constant level, summarized in Table I of Fig. 2(a). We clarify that the resin percentage is assigned to the average dielectric constant value of configuration types A, B, C.

III. OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

We present an overview of the methodology flow chart in Fig. 2(a). We demonstrate our methodology by transforming a two-dimensional periodic metagrating to a 3D-printable one. The metagrating is assumed to be infinite in extent along the y axis, following the convention of Fig. 2(b). An extruded device is shown in Fig. 2(c), to highlight its two-dimensional nature. The metagrating refracts a normally incident wave, with the magnetic field oriented along the y axis and the electric field parallel to the $x - z$ plane, to a -77° angle. As the device is periodic along the x axis, having a period D , as shown in Fig. 2(b), we examine the device's unit cell. Throughout the paper, we will adopt the axes convention as well as the direction and polarization of the incident wave depicted in Fig. 2(b). Our algorithm, termed BINACONN, takes a discrete dielectric constant profile ($E_{\text{mat},d}$) and the resin percentage that achieves each dielectric constant level [Table I of Fig. 2(a)] as inputs, and produces a 3D-printable binary and connected device. The pre-processing steps include (i) the conversion of a continuous dielectric constant profile, obtained by an inverse design process, to a discrete one, with the necessary number of intermediate levels, and (ii) the calculation of the resin percentage that achieves each intermediate dielectric constant level, described in Sec. II. In the following sections, we will describe the BINACONN algorithm and demonstrate the methodology by designing a 3D-printable wide-angle refraction metagrating with its performance being very close to the continuous case.

TABLE I

Dielectric Constant	Resin Percentage (%)
1	0
1.28	23
1.57	44
1.85	57
2.13	75
2.42	88
2.7	100

FIG. 2. (a) Overview of the methodology flow chart. The conversion of a continuous dielectric constant profile to a discrete one, with the necessary number of intermediate levels, is the pre-processing step of BINACONN. The BINACONN algorithm takes a discrete dielectric constant profile ($E_{\text{mat},d}$) and the resin percentage that achieves each dielectric constant level as inputs and produces a 3D-printable binary and connected device. (b) The periodic nature of the device is highlighted. The device is periodic along the x axis with a period D . The axes convention and the incident wave direction and polarization assumed throughout the paper are also denoted. (c) The device extends infinitely along the y axis; it is a 2D device.

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IV. RENDERING THE DEVICE BINARY AND CONNECTED (BINACONN)

A. Checking for connectivity

All parts of the structure must be connected to ensure that the metagrating is 3D-printable. To check if the device is connected, we use basic concepts of graph theory. Graph theory has been recently used as part of a topology-optimization formulation,²⁹ to impose fabrication constraints related to additive manufacturing. We form an undirected and unweighted graph $G(V, E)$. The graph consists of a set of nodes V , which in our case are all non-air cells, with a relative dielectric permittivity larger than one ($\epsilon_r > 1$). A graph also consists of a set of edges E that show the connections between the nodes. An edge connects nodes u and v if v is one of the four immediate spatial neighbors (west, north, east, south) of u . The graph is undirected, which means that an edge has no direction; it symmetrically connects two nodes. All edges of this graph have a weight equal to one, as all connections are equally important; hence, the graph is unweighted. In our work, we will use graphs to check if the device is connected. We note that nodes that are placed diagonally and share only a corner, are not connected, as the cells that correspond to the nodes cannot be 3D-printed as a single connected component. We use MATLAB's function `conncomp`^{30,31} to calculate the connected components of the graph G . A connected component is a subset of nodes S where every node $u \in S$ is reachable by every other node $v \in S$. The entire device is connected if there is a single component in the graph that contains all nodes. As an additional pre-processing step of BINACONN, we check if the device made by the discrete yet non-binary materials is connected. Ideally, we want to start with a fully connected device, or alternatively, with one where only a very small and thus negligible number of cells is not connected and can be omitted without compromising the device's performance. We illustrate the nodes and edges of graph G in Fig. 2(a). In this example, two connected components are formed, with one of them having only four nodes.

B. The BINACONN algorithm

The BINACONN algorithm is implemented for each intermediate dielectric constant level $\epsilon_{r,d}$ and assigns air or resin to all cells of an $\epsilon_{r,d}$ dielectric constant. In the BINACONN algorithm, we try to meet the assigned air/resin percentage on each material component instead of the entire material of $\epsilon_{r,d}$; this increases the likelihood of resin and air being more uniformly distributed across the device. To that end, we form a new graph G_d , with the nodes of G_d being the cells of intermediate dielectric-constant level $\epsilon_{r,d}$. We will try to satisfy the air/resin percentage on each component of the graph G_d . Hence, we start by finding the components of the graph G_d (line 2 of Algorithm 1). In Fig. 3(b) we highlight in black the material with $\epsilon_{r,d} = 1.28$. The material is present in different areas of the device, with the corresponding graph $G_{1,28}$ consisting of 28 connected components. The largest component is enclosed in a red ellipse.

For each component i of the graph G_d (cells of material $\epsilon_{r,d}$), we find the nodes that belong to the component i (line 4 of Algorithm 1) and remove the necessary number of nodes (n_{rem}). The removed nodes are set to air ($\epsilon_r = 1$), and the remaining

FIG. 3. (a) The graph G , with all non-air materials of the device considered as the graph nodes and immediate neighbors connected by an edge. (b) The graph $G_{1,28}$ of cells with $\epsilon_{r,d} = 1.28$ with 28 connected components. The nodes of each component are shown in black. The largest component is enclosed in a red ellipse.

nodes are set to be resin ($\epsilon_r = 2.7$). The number of the nodes that we should remove (n_{rem}) is calculated as $n_{rem} = (1 - p_{res}) n_{group}$, where p_{res} is the resin percentage of Fig. 2(a) and n_{group} is the number of nodes within the component i of graph G_d . Sparser materials are more challenging to implement, as a greater number of nodes must be removed. Therefore, we start with sparser materials and move on to denser ones.

We use a uniform random distribution to determine which cells will be assigned to air in each material component. We obtain manufacturable devices with different resin distributions by running the BINACONN algorithm with a different random seed.

ALGORITHM 1. Substituting materials of non-feasible dielectric constant levels with air-resin combinations ensuring connectivity.

```

1: procedure BINACONN  $E_{mat,d}, \epsilon_{r,d}, p_{rem}$  where  $p_{rem}$  is the resin
   percentage in material  $\epsilon_{r,d}$  and  $E_{mat,d}$  is the discrete material
   profile
2:    $comp \leftarrow$  Find the components of graph  $G_d$ 
3:   for  $i = 1 : 1 : n_{comp}$  do
4:      $[coord, n_{group}] \leftarrow$  Find the nodes in each component  $i$ 
5:      $n_{rem} \leftarrow$  Calculate the number of nodes to be removed in the
   component  $i$ 
6:      $E_{mat,b} \leftarrow$  Remove the nodes in component  $i$ . A uniform
   random distribution determines the nodes that will be removed
   A node is removed if it does not disconnect the device and
   a if  $n_{rem}$  has not been reached
7:      $E_{mat,d} \leftarrow$  Update the material profile by assigning air to the
   removed nodes and resin to the remaining
8:   end for
9:   return the updated material profile  $E_{mat,d}$ 
10: end procedure

```

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Before removing a node from a component, we must ensure that the removal of the node will not disconnect the total device. We only remove nodes that, upon removal, would not increase the total number of components of graph G of the global structure, i.e., they are not articulation points.³⁰ At each step, we check that the total graph remains connected (line 6 of Algorithm 1). By using the BINACONN algorithm on each intermediate material level, we obtain a manufacturable device ($E_{\text{mat,b}}$), which is binary and connected.

V. SYNTHESIS OF A 3D-PRINTABLE METAGRATING

A. Metagrating with a continuous dielectric constant profile

We design a wide-angle refractive metagrating of high normalized diffraction efficiency, which refracts a normally incident plane wave to a wide angle of -77° with respect to normal incidence with the polarization of Fig. 2(b). The continuous dielectric constant profile of the metagrating is obtained by inverse design, using an objective-first optimization algorithm.¹⁷ We use the existing implementation of the objective-first optimization³² and assign the propagation characteristics of a normally incident plane wave with the magnetic field oriented along the y axis [Fig. 2(b)] to the input plane and those of a plane wave of the same polarization refracted in the direction of the -1 space harmonic to the output plane. We note that the quality of the solution heavily depends on the initial configuration and that the method does not guarantee convergence to an optimal solution. We consider a baseline model from the literature,⁶ shown in Fig. 5(b), and scale it to operate around 10 GHz. We consider the real part of the dielectric constant of Formlabs Clear V4 resin, $\epsilon_r = 2.7$. This baseline model is a wide-angle, low-index metagrating of a simpler geometric shape. By the inverse design, we aim at an even higher normalized diffraction efficiency around -77° . We use the objective-first optimization on a computational domain of 141×43 uniform grid cells [Fig. 4(a)], with each cell of size $\lambda/42 \times \lambda/42$, where λ is the free-space wavelength at 10 GHz. Each cell can assume dielectric constant values within the continuous range $\epsilon_r = \{1, 2.7\}$. The optimization is carried out multiple times, each time starting from different initial configurations. We selected the best-performing solution, with significantly higher normalized diffraction efficiency than the baseline model.

The diffraction efficiency of the -1 space harmonic, corresponding to the desired diffraction angle is shown in Fig. 5(a) for both the baseline and optimized configurations. As dielectric losses are not considered, the -1 diffraction order efficiency is equal to the normalized -1 diffraction order efficiency with respect to the total diffracted power. The diffraction efficiency is calculated by both the FEM periodic solver of COMSOL Multiphysics[®] and the rigorous coupled-wave analysis (RCWA) solver of RETICOLO software,³³ with good agreement observed in the results of the two solvers. As the same FEM computational setup will be used to simulate the performance of all considered metagratings, starting from the baseline metagrating up to the final optimized manufacturable design, we summarize the computational setup details. The RF module of COMSOL Multiphysics is used for the simulations. Periodic boundary conditions are imposed along the x axis, following the axis convention of Fig. 2(b). Periodic port boundary

FIG. 4. (a) The dense uniform grid used in the inverse design. Each grid cell is of size $\lambda/42 \times \lambda/42$, λ being the free-space wavelength at 10 GHz, and can assume values between the dielectric constant of air and resin. One of the cells is shown next to the grid, along with its dimensions. (b) The optimized configuration with continuous values of the dielectric constant.

conditions are imposed on the input and output ports. The device is excited by a normally incident plane wave with the magnetic field oriented along the y axis [Fig. 2(b)]. The device is simulated in the frequency range $\{9.6, 10.6\}$ GHz. In the range of 9.9–10.4 GHz, which corresponds to deflection angles between -80° and -70° , the average calculated -1 diffraction order efficiency, by the RCWA results, is about 76% for the baseline device and 89% for the optimized device. We will render the optimized device 3D-printable, aiming at a performance as close as possible to the continuous case.

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FIG. 5. (a) The -1 diffraction order efficiency of the baseline configuration, by the FEM and RCWA periodic solvers, and the optimized metagrating with a continuous range of dielectric constant values. (b) Baseline configuration.

B. Rendering the continuous dielectric constant profile discrete

The BINACONN algorithm takes a discrete dielectric constant profile $E_{mat,d}$ as input. Hence, we must transform the continuous dielectric constant profile obtained by the inverse design to a discrete one, with the device's performance preserved as close as possible to that of the continuous case. We note that this transformation is not part of the BINACONN algorithm; it is a necessary pre-processing step to obtain $E_{mat,d}$, which is an input to the BINACONN algorithm. To that end, we perform simulations of the device, using the RCWA solver, with a different number of discrete levels preserved in each simulation. All continuous dielectric constant values are substituted by the closest discrete value. By adding more intermediate levels, the performance approaches that of the continuous case. We select the device with a discrete dielectric profile, which achieves performance as close as possible to that of the continuous case and for which adding more material levels offers negligible improvement on the performance. In Fig. 6, we compare the efficiency of the continuous case, the case of two, five, seven, and nine dielectric constant levels. We note that if we consider just two dielectric constant levels, corresponding to air and resin, the performance of the metagrating is significantly impacted. Although five levels are quite close to the continuous case, seven levels are in even better agreement, as verified by RCWA simulations. Nine levels only offer negligible improvement. Hence, we proceed with the seven-material level design. We also verify the RCWA results with the COMSOL Multiphysics® RF-module solver in Fig. 7, for the case of seven dielectric constant levels. The FEM is in very good agreement with the RCWA solver.

We also examine whether the metagrating of seven material levels is fully connected. In case the graph G has more than one component, we also check how many nodes are not connected to the main and larger component. Two connected components are formed for the graph corresponding to the device with seven material levels: the main one with 4895 nodes, and a second minor one with only 4 nodes. We further checked that the component of 4 nodes, has a dielectric constant of $\epsilon_r = 1.28$. According to Table I

FIG. 6. The -1 diffraction order efficiency of the metagrating with a continuous range, 2, 5, 7, and 9 levels of dielectric constant values, calculated by the RCWA solver.

FIG. 7. Comparison of the FEM and RCWA -1 diffraction order efficiency results of the metagrating with 7 dielectric constant levels.

of Fig. 2(a), one node at most will remain as resin after implementing the BINACONN algorithm. Therefore, we proceed with the 7-level design, and we will verify by simulations that ignoring one cell does not affect the performance. We note that if the metagrating performance was impacted, we would consider more material levels. We show each material of the 7-level design in a different color in Fig. 8, confirming the existence of irregular shapes within a specific material as well as thin and rapidly interchanged layers.

FIG. 8. Metagrating with each of the seven materials shown in a different color.

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C. Realizing a 3D-printable device

We implement the BINACONN algorithm for each material level, moving from the sparser to the denser material. As discussed in Sec. IV, a uniform random distribution is used to determine which cells will be assigned to air in each component. We obtain manufacturable devices with different resin distributions by running the BINACONN algorithm with a different random seed. We produce ten different manufacturable devices; a different number of devices may be needed depending on the application.

Devices consisting of air/resin configurations with more material volumes and finer internal features better approximate the performance of the non-manufacturable device. Hence, we describe an approach to measure which manufacturable device has the most material volumes or the finest internal features. For each cell of the manufacturable device, (i) we consider its local neighborhood consisting of all cells within a fixed-sized rectangular window centered at the cell, and (ii) we calculate the percentage of resin cells within this neighborhood. Ideally, the resin percentage in the neighborhood of a cell should match the assigned air/resin ratio for the cell's initial dielectric constant. Thus, the resin percentage across all cells of the same initial dielectric constant value should be constant. In practice, we can quantify deviations from the ideal case by computing how much the resin percentages vary across cells that belong to the same initial dielectric constant. Lower variation indicates a configuration that has the most material volumes and the finest internal features uniformly distributed across the device profile. This measure provides an initial indication of the best-performing manufacturable device, which is device 6.

We select the best-performing manufacturable device by simulating all manufacturable devices and comparing their performance to the non-manufacturable device. Each manufacturable device is simulated using the FEM solver of Comsol Multiphysics, with the computational setup described in Sec. V A. The efficiency of the -1 diffraction order is shown in Fig. 9 for each manufacturable device and the non-manufacturable device with seven material levels. We calculate the corresponding average efficiency of all ten manufacturable devices in the frequency range of 9.9–10.4 GHz.

FIG. 9. The -1 diffraction order efficiency of the manufacturable metagratings obtained by BINACONN. As BINACONN uses a randomization process to move across each component, we compare the results of ten BINACONN outcomes.

The best-performing manufacturable device is the one with the closest average efficiency to the device with seven material levels (black dashed line of Fig. 9). Based on this criterion, the manufacturable device # 6 (black solid line of Fig. 9) is selected as the best-performing manufacturable device, which is in agreement with the initial indication. The manufacturable device has an average efficiency of 87.9% in the 9.9–10.4 GHz range, while the non-manufacturable device with seven material levels has an efficiency of 89.2% in the same range. The selected configuration is shown in Fig. 10(a). The manufacturable 2D profile of the unitcell is shown in Fig. 10(b), after having removed the single disconnected cell. The efficiency of the manufacturable metagrating remains identical after the removal of the cell. We observe that although the pattern is very detailed, it can be manufactured by the Formlabs Form 3 printer, as all air holes have a diameter greater than 0.5 mm,³⁴ adhering to the printer specifications.

To achieve a performance close to that of the continuous case, a high resolution, i.e., a dense grid of cells, is needed. A coarse grid would make it very challenging or even infeasible to remove the necessary number of nodes from each component while also ensuring connectivity, due to the reduced number of degrees of freedom. By using a dense grid with a cell size of $\lambda/42 \times \lambda/42$, the BINACONN algorithm has produced a 3D-printable device with an average efficiency of approximately 1.3% lower than the non-manufacturable device with seven material levels. The reduction of the average efficiency by close to 1% in exchange for rendering this complex-shaped device manufacturable is a reasonable and satisfactory trade-off.

FIG. 10. (a) Optimized manufacturable and binary metagrating configuration. (b) The optimized manufacturable and binary metagrating configuration after removing the single disconnected cell.

FIG. 11. Comparison of the -1 diffraction order efficiency, calculated by FEM, of the optimized metagrating assuming (a) a continuous dielectric constant profile and (b) the manufacturable device.

D. Validation of our approach

In the previous subsection, we selected the 3D-printable device of Fig. 10(b) that has the closest -1 diffraction order efficiency to the device of seven material levels. We validate our methodology by comparing the performance of the manufacturable device to that of the initial device with the continuous dielectric profile in Fig. 11. The comparison is based on simulations using the commercially available FEM solver of Comsol Multiphysics for both devices (setup of Sec. V A). The manufacturable device produced by BINACONN has an average efficiency approximately 1% lower than that of the device with a continuous material profile. The simulations of Fig. 11 provide sufficient validation for our methodology, since we have ensured that the devices produced by BINACONN can be manufactured, by taking into account the specifications provided for the Formlabs Form 3 printer.³⁴

E. Additional characterization of the manufacturable device

We also present the normalized diffraction efficiencies of all diffraction orders, as well as plots of the magnetic field, to fully characterize the manufacturable device. The FEM simulation setup of Sec. V A is used here as well. Dielectric losses are included in the simulation. We present the real part of the magnetic field intensity component $\Re\{H_y\}$ at $f = 10$ GHz [Fig. 12(a)] and at $f = 10.14$ GHz [Fig. 12(b)], with the latter corresponding to the frequency of maximum normalized -1 diffraction order efficiency. We observe that, indeed, the output wave is refracted into a wide angle, -77° at $f = 10$ GHz and -74° at $f = 10.14$ GHz.

We present all supported normalized diffraction order efficiencies, i.e., $-1, 0, 1$ at the input and output ports of the device, with respect to the total diffracted power. The normalized diffraction order efficiency is calculated as

$$E_i^{R/T} = \frac{P_i^{R/T}}{\sum_{n=-1}^1 P_n^R + \sum_{n=-1}^1 P_n^T}, \quad (1)$$

FIG. 12. The real part of the magnetic field intensity component $\Re\{H_y\}$ of the simulated manufacturable metagrating at (a) $f = 10$ GHz and (b) $f = 10.14$ GHz.

where $E_i^{R/T}$ is the normalized diffraction efficiency of order $i = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ and R/T denotes reflection, calculated on the input port, or transmission, calculated on the output port. The nominator $P_i^{R/T}$ is power diffracted in the direction of the diffraction order i on each port R/T , respectively. The denominator is the sum of the power diffracted into all diffraction orders.

The normalized efficiency of each diffraction order is shown in Fig. 13. Below 9.75 GHz the main power is transmitted to the zeroth diffraction order, whereas the desired -1 diffraction order is dominant above 9.8 GHz. Above 10.2 GHz, the efficiency of the -1 diffraction order in reflection starts to become somewhat more significant, with a normalized power efficiency of up to 0.1. The results confirm that more than 90% of the diffracted power is transmitted in the desired direction between 9.96 and 10.26 GHz.

FIG. 13. Normalized diffraction order efficiency with respect to the total diffracted power. The results are shown for the manufacturable metagrating.

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FIG. 14. Optimized metagrating with all single air cells eliminated. (a) Geometry and (b) the -1 diffraction order efficiency.

VI. AVOIDING SMALL AIR HOLES

Avoiding very small air holes may make the devices less prone to fabrication errors, especially for higher frequencies. To promote larger air regions, we present an optional step of eliminating single air cells from the device of Fig. 10(b). We form a graph G_a of all air cells and find the graph components. The components composed of a single node correspond to the single air cells. We search for the nearest neighbor of each single node, i.e., the closest air cell, which we denote v_{nm} . We then try to remove, i.e., assign air, to one of the immediate neighbors of node v_{nm} , while checking that the removal of the node does not disconnect the entire device. Once we have assigned air to an immediate neighbor of v_{nm} , we also assign resin to the single air cell. This process is followed multiple times, using the closest available neighbors, until all single cells are removed. The device with no single air cells is shown in Fig. 14(a). The device is simulated in Comsol Multiphysics, as in Sec. V A. As this an optional step of the BINACONN algorithm, losses are not considered. The efficiency of this device is compared against the outcome of BINACONN and the configuration that uses seven materials in Fig. 14(b) and very good agreement is observed. By eliminating all single air cells and by enlarging one of the closest air regions instead, we can enhance manufacturability while maintaining a high performance.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we introduced a systematic process to synthesize 3D-printable devices. Each intermediate material layer is substituted by air/resin configurations of a necessary percentage, to achieve the effective medium response. Importantly, we ensure connectivity of the device, by treating each non-air cell as a graph node, and by checking that each node that is removed does not make the entire device disconnected. Assigning an air/resin percentage instead of a specific unit cell to each material layer provides additional degrees of freedom, which allows the realization of connected devices with performance very close to the continuous case. This is especially important for complex devices with non-intuitive and rapidly varying material properties, as are the devices obtained by inverse design. As a proof of concept, the proposed

methodology is used to design a 2D wide-angle refracting metagrating that preserves the performance of a device of continuous dielectric constant values, as validated by FEM simulations. The proposed approach can be also extended toward 3D devices, as all processes are also applicable to 3D structures.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Maria-Thaleia Passia: Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (lead); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead). **Steven A. Cummer:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Resources (lead); Supervision (lead); Writing – review & editing (lead).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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